

TOWARDS A PRIVACY-AWARE REPRODUCIBLE MACHINE LEARNING PIPELINE FOR OPEN DATA

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Abstract

Different definitions, structures, guidelines, and architectures for ML pipelines exist. However, most of these guidelines do not require a level of privacy and anonymization for sensitive data and also do not account for reproducibility. To address the mentioned problems of providing a platform for open sourcing, deployment, and evaluation of reproducible machine learning models, steps necessary to reproduce these models, and privacy-aware data storage and distribution, we propose a Privacy-Aware Machine Learning Pipeline solution. The first part of this research focuses on the analysis of existing machine learning pipeline structures, the necessary steps to create these structures to accommodate machine learning processes, and their connection to open data and privacy. Finally, the steps necessary for the creation of an ML Pipeline for an Open Search System with Kubeflow have been described and outlined, together with future ideas and possible weaknesses.

INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) is an impactful topic that has been integrated into diverse areas such as medicine, decision support, navigation, and more. Building an ML application is a difficult task that one person cannot usually do. To succeed in building ML applications and to integrate ML into organizations, projects, and ideas, it is necessary to collaborate with a group of individuals or between multiple groups. For example, one group acquires raw data and labels the data from a different group to construct training data. Multiple groups need to collaborate to build an ML model. A different group can then use this model to solve business problems [1, 2].

Machine learning applications are pipelines combining different processes and different groups of experts [3]. As ML becomes more competitive, many organizations and researchers feel driven to rush in on the implementation without following procedures and not documenting methods, all for faster results. ML is facing a replication crisis, such as the ones that have been seen in psychology, medicine, and other fields over the past decades [4]. Researchers have found it difficult to reproduce many key results, raising doubts about research methods and publication protocols. Without the ability to replicate previous results, it is difficult to compare results to determine if newly developed algorithms are better than the previous ones [1, 2].

To create novel and reproducible ML algorithms, multiple steps need to be taken; in some cases, they are done by one

team or by multiple teams. Example steps include data collection, data cleaning, model training, model delivery, model evaluation, and others. Different tools can be used in any of the previously mentioned steps, for example, cloud providers (Amazon S3¹, OneDrive², Gdrive³, etc.) can be used for data storage, git (e.g. gitlab⁴, github⁵, etc.) can be used for keeping track of the code, Python libraries for model creation, docker for containerization, and more. The combination of the previously mentioned steps and tools with documentation and instructions form an ML pipeline. However, only a few solutions combine all the individual tools used for specific steps of an ML pipeline together [2,3].

Personalization through ML offers powerful tools for enhancing the user experience in diverse systems. At the same time, it raises new privacy concerns that may discourage the adoption of personalization in ML [5]. Despite privacy challenges, user data records have widely been used to study various behavioral patterns, interactions, problems, and others. Furthermore, many ML models have been trained on this type of data to perform various tasks, such as creating predictive models, recommender systems, detecting user groups, and more [6]. Usage of private data for ML has not been without abuse, the Cambridge Analytica Facebook scandal led to the revelation that an estimated 87 million Facebook user profiles had been harvested without the users' consent and knowledge. These data were used to influence the opinion of individuals, by recommending specific news articles and displaying specific content to users [7].

When distributing sensitive information, it is important to follow guidelines, which can be given by countries, public entities, or even organizations themselves. Most of these guidelines require a level of privacy and anonymization for sensitive data [8]. With a higher degree of anonymization, the less useful the information is [9]. Open Data is the term used to describe data available freely for anyone to use for analysis and research [8]. with the goal to increase accountability and transparency.

To address the mentioned problems of providing a platform for open sourcing, deployment, and evaluation of reproducible machine learning models, steps necessary to reproduce these models, and privacy-aware data storage and distribution, we propose a privacy-aware machine learning pipeline solution.

¹ <https://aws.amazon.com/aws/s3>

² <https://onedrive.live.com>

³ <http://drive.google.com/>

⁴ <http://gitlab.com>

⁵ <http://github.com>

Figure 1: Open ML Pipeline Steps based on AutoML [10]

Based on the statements expressed above, the main research questions are:

- **RQ1:** How can Open Data facilitate the creation of privacy-respecting ML Pipelines?
- **RQ2:** How can Open Data-based ML pipelines be used for the implementation of ML algorithms while ensuring reproducibility using search as the application domain for ML algorithms?

The first part of this research focuses on the analysis of existing machine learning pipeline structures, the necessary steps to create these structures to accommodate machine learning processes, and their connection to open data, privacy, and data storage. In the second part of this research, we describe the necessary implementation steps for constructing such a pipeline for large interconnected organizations on the example of CERN infrastructure. Next we focus on the use case of implementing ML algorithms for search using Open Data and how can reproducibility be ensured. The paper concludes with an explanation of the drawbacks, lessons learned, and future steps to facilitate such machine learning pipelines.

BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Reproducibility and Open Science

Reproducibility can be defined as the ability to replicate a model that produces the same result as the original model given the same input data [2]. It is also essential to promote open and accessible research, the use of robust experimental workflows, and to allow researchers to quickly convert ideas into practice while reducing unintentional errors [11]. Similar to the principles of reproducibility, a movement to conduct science transparently by making code, data, scientific communications, and any other research artifact publicly available and easily accessible over the long-term is called Open Science [8].

Machine Learning and Privacy

ML refers to algorithms and statistical models used by computer systems to efficiently perform specific tasks without the use of explicit instructions [12]. The need to provide personalized and evolving artificial intelligence (AI) services such as voice assistant, word suggestion, facial recognition, and smart video feeds has increased the amount of data generated. In most of these applications, machine learning models are refined by continuously feeding in new user data (as features) and their feedback (as labels). However, these data, such as type history, web access logs, and frequently visited locations, often include sensitive and private information [13]. Because of these risks, initial work on mitigating privacy risks during the machine learning process focuses on privacy challenges and risks associated with the ML models. Commonly used methods for protecting sensitive data in ML processes are Local Differential Privacy and Federated Machine Learning [13, 14].

Machine Learning Pipelines

The objective of an ML pipeline is to outline the ML model creation process with a series of steps that take a model from initial development to deployment and usage. It is an iterative process, as each step continuously improves and builds a more useful model [15]. Microsoft, Amazon, IBM, and other cloud providers have launched ML as a service that reduces costs, time, and risk of building ML infrastructure by offering premade generic ML tools. These tools recreate specific steps of ML pipelines, allowing fast implementation of ML algorithms [16].

Based on previous research, the basic steps and substeps of the ML pipelines have been identified and synthesized [2,3,6,15]. These steps shown in Figure 1 are Data Ingestion, Feature Engineering, Model Building, and Predictions.

Data Ingestion is the process of moving data from one or more sources to a destination where they can be stored and further analyzed. In addition to the collection and aggregation process, the data ingestion process can include anonymization steps. Where private attributes are removed

or anonymized to protect user privacy. The results of this step can be also used to publish collected data (e.g. organizational data) as open data [10, 17].

Feature Engineering is the process of selecting, manipulating, and transforming raw data into features that can be used in ML. Feature engineering consists of four main steps. First, the data are pre-processed to remove outliers and noise. Then the preprocessed data is transformed to fit a data type and/or format. From the transformed data, the features are extracted using various feature extraction methods. After extracting features from the data, the last step is to select the most appropriate features given the data and the task [2, 18].

Model Building An ML model is built by learning and generalizing the training data and then applying that acquired knowledge to new data. The three main stages of model building are model training, model evaluation, and model validation [10, 18, 19].

1. **Model Training** - It is the initial step of the model-building process, in this step an ML algorithm/s are selected for model building. Training data is fed to the selected algorithms to help identify and learn adequate values for all attributes involved [10, 19].
2. **Model Evaluation** - This step focuses on finding the most suitable model representing the input data and determining how the chosen model will perform in the future. Model performance evaluation is not done with training data because it can generate overoptimistic and overfitted models. To avoid these issues evaluation methods use data from the initial dataset not used for model training [19].
3. **Model Validation** - It refers to the process of confirming that the model achieves its intended objective. This involves the confirmation that the model is predictive under the requirements of its intended use [18, 19].

If the models created in this phase do not perform as expected, it is possible to go back to Feature Engineering and use the knowledge gathered to improve and select better features.

Predictions After the creation, evaluation, and validation of the model, the next step includes making the implemented ML model available to end users. It requires the model to be deployed in applications and/or to an endpoint for usage. Additionally, the model's performance needs monitoring to extract information for future developments and improvements. If the results of the monitoring phase show that the created model does not perform in an expected manner, it is possible to go back to either the Model Building or Feature Engineering phase and improve the ML model. Data collected from the monitoring phase can be used as additional information to create a better ML model or to select features from the old model [10, 18, 19].

TOWARDS A PRIVACY AWARE MACHINE LEARNING PIPELINE

Taking into account the previously defined steps for ML pipelines, multiple software packages provide the necessary tools to reproduce the mentioned steps. Due to the positive impact of open source software and principles on reproducibility, it was decided to focus on open source solutions. Based on GitHub reviews, usage, frequency of updates, and community interaction the most popular open source projects are MLflow⁶, Flyte⁷, ML Run⁸, and KubeFlow⁹. Table 1 provides a summarization of the main functionalities necessary for the creation of an ML pipeline. Based on it, MLFlow and Flyte do not provide the options to orchestrate pipelines and deploy models, which makes them not a good option for the creation of reproducible ML pipelines. Since it is not possible to define the steps necessary to create pipelines. It is also not possible to create a deployment version of an ML model created by these software packages. On the other hand, ML Run provides the necessary elements for the creation of the ML pipeline, but KubeFlow provides better documentation and an interactive dashboard. Taking this into account, organizational constraints and the level of features provided, KubeFlow was selected.

Figure 2: Kubeflow components in the ML workflow ¹⁰

Figure 2 describes the flow diagram provided by the Kubeflow documentation for the creation of ML pipelines with

⁶ <https://mlflow.org/>

⁷ <https://flyte.org/>

⁸ <https://www.mlrun.org/>

⁹ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/started/architecture/>

	Kubeflow	MLFlow	Flyte	ML Run
Open Source	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Language	Python	Python/R/Java	Python	Python
Documentation	Very Good	Good	Poor	Good
Tracking and Versioning	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Pipeline Orchestration	Yes	No	No	Yes
Model Deployment	Yes	No	No	Yes
Scheduler	Yes	No	Yes	No
Dashboard	Yes	Yes	Yes	Limited Functionality

Table 1: Software Packages for Building ML Applications

tools that can be used in each step. The experimental and production phases are the two main phases for developing and deploying an ML system that have been identified by the Kubeflow community.

In the experimental phase, the model is developed, tested, and updated based on initial assumptions to produce favorable results. This phase is comprised of four steps. First, it is necessary to identify the ML problem. The data are then collected and analyzed for training. Afterward, an ML framework and algorithm are selected, and the initial version of the model is produced. The last step includes experimenting with the data and with model training and tuning the model’s hyperparameters to ensure the most efficient processing and the most accurate results possible.

The ML model is reproduced, trained, and deployed in the production phase. To ensure that the model behaves consistently during training and prediction, the transformation of the data into a format for model training from the experimental phase must also be reproduced in the production phases. After the data transformation step, the ML model is trained and served for online predictions. In addition, the performance of the model is monitored and the prediction results are evaluated and processed for model tuning and retraining.

Based on the steps defined in Figure 1 and the previously defined Kubeflow workflow, it is noticeable that steps of the workflow can be directly mapped to Open ML Pipeline steps. The Kubeflow workflows will produce an ML model that aims to solve the identified problem, but it does not ensure reproducibility. To ensure reproducibility, it is necessary to expand the steps outlined in Kubeflow ML workflow based on Figure 1. Additional steps are needed to ensure that the data and algorithms used in the ML pipeline are available without restrictions. These steps aim to produce open data by removing sensitive information from the original dataset. Following the DataLift framework for open source organization data, it is necessary to publish data with the definition of the purpose and scope of the data, the classification of attributes and the risks of the attributes [17]. Additionally, the configuration of the ML pipeline with the used algorithms needs to be published. The data and configurations can be published to a public repository (e.g. Zenodo, Github, Gitlab, etc.). Expanding the Kubeflow ML workflow with

regards to reproducibility, the number of ambiguities related to reproducing ML experiments is minimized while ensuring that reproducing results from the data becomes a straightforward process.

Reproducible Open Data and Search Use Case

The previously defined generic ML pipeline steps and selected ML pipeline framework can be used for a variety of ML applications. To demonstrate the real-world application of Kubeflow, this section focuses on determining the usability and application of Kubeflow for the creation of an ML pipeline for an Open Search System based on Open Data. Many components have to work together to implement a successful search system, from securely storing information to providing an easy-to-use interface for the user. Focusing on the open search application domain, we concentrate on the creation of an ML Pipeline that produces an ML model for relevant ranked information retrieval based on input parameters. Figure 3 represents the open search structure proposed at the 3rd International Open Search Symposium extended with ML Pipelines. The structure integrates concepts of information retrieval in large organizations, information sharing between external and internal organizational users, and the creation of user profiles that respect client privacy.

Data Ingestion

As previously mentioned this step focuses on gathering data for ML model building. With an open search system, it is necessary first to transform organizational and user data into anonymous data. Otherwise, due to privacy issues, these data could not be used for ML and model building. Additionally, users must control how their data is used and processed. This implies that the data ingestion process can only take place when all personal information is removed from the query or if the user has explicitly approved the use of the data for model training. In the case that the user has approved data usage for model training, it still needs to be anonymized.

Feature Engineering

After the data ingestion step, feature engineering starts by removing outliers and reducing the noise from the data. Based on the use case defined for the ML pipeline, the data

Figure 3: Conceptual Integration Diagram of the Open Search System for Large and Highly Connected Organizations and ML Pipelines

is transformed to fit the predefined data format. From the transformed data, all possible features are extracted. Based on domain knowledge and analysis, potential features are selected for the model-building step. For an ML pipeline that works with anonymized user data, it is necessary to protect user privacy by avoiding the creation of features that could enable user identification based on anonymized data. Additionally, anonymized ingested data is published to be freely available for other services, ensuring reproducibility.

Model Building

The data created with the selected features are separated into test and validation data sets. Both data sets are comprised of input values (anonymized user queries) and output values (preferred user results). Based on data attributes (e.g., data distribution, sparseness, etc.), defined initial problem, and hardware and software constraints, an ML model is selected and trained on the test data. The built model is evaluated using statistical accuracy metrics and/or decision support accuracy metrics. In the case where the model evaluation yields positive results, it is validated by applying the model to the validation data and comparing if the model predicts the output values correctly and to what degree. To ensure reproducibility, the ML model and the metadata linked to the model must be stored and distributed as open data.

If the evaluation or validation steps do not produce satisfactory results, it is possible to repeat the step with a different model. Additionally, it is possible to go back to feature en-

gineering and extract new features based on findings from this step

Predictions

The last step of the ML pipeline is providing a usable endpoint for the created ML model. A usable endpoint is a standalone endpoint (e.g. REST API endpoint) that can be reached by various applications and generate predictions based on the input data. The input data must be in the same format used to train and validate the model. In contrast to traditional methods where user profiles are stored on a central module, for the proposed Open Search System user profiles must be stored locally.

For local user profiling presented in Figure 3, it is necessary to share the created ML model with different users for local usage. Users would be able to filter results based on a local model without revealing personal information to the ML Pipeline and Open Search System.

FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSION

An Open Search System needs to address many challenges to create an ML model and/or ML pipeline that is privacy aware. These include efficiently storing, generating, maintaining, and sharing anonymous user information. The drawbacks and benefits of creating a privacy-aware ML model must be analyzed in depth to find new ways to educate users about the data that are being collected and processed.

In conclusion, steps necessary for the creation of an ML Pipeline for an Open Search System with Kubeflow have been described and outlined, as well as ideas for future

ideas and possible weaknesses. A generic guideline for ML pipeline creation has been synthesized, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of each step. Four software packages for building ML applications and pipelines have been analyzed, and their usability has been assessed.

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¹¹<http://www.OpenWebSearch.EU>